

Business Penetration through Print Media: A Review of Select Enablers

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Abstract—It's an era of high competition, dynamism and complexities which have forced organizations to change dramatically due to rising customer expectations. Marketers are under constant pressure to deliver finest to their customers. With the advent of technology, marketers have identified latest advertising media options to reach out to target audience. But the conventional ways of print advertisements still holds a deeper penetration and coverage. Various researchers and practitioners have studied the area of print media advertising and have tried to identify and implement advertisement effectiveness enablers. The purpose of this paper is to suggest select enablers for print media in Indian context using an integrated approach of review of literature and investigative interviews with academicians and experts from the area of advertising.

Keywords—Advertising, Advertisement Effectiveness, Competition, Print Media.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE fierce competition, dynamism and operational complexities in today's market are led by advances in technology, increased globalization and tremendous improvement in information availability to customers [1]. Markets are cluttered worldwide and an organization believe in two broad ways of increasing profitability viz. by decreasing product's cost or by expanding existing market share. Past researchers have highlighted that though cost reduction is one of the profitable ways but it has its own limitations [2], [3]. As a result, increasing market share seems more practical to organizations which has proven evidences for positive association between increased advertising and improved market share.

Advertising is defined as non personal, paid form of communication usually pervasive in nature about products, services or ideas and with an identified sponsor [4]. It represents an important means by which organizations communicate with their customers, both current and potential [5]. Though marketers have identified various latest advertising media options to reach out to target audience; the traditional means of print advertising is still a significant element of an organization's promotional and media mix in India with several advantages as depicted in Fig. 1.

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Fig. 1 Several Advantages of Print Media

In contrast to the West, the Indian newspaper industry will grow strongly for another decade and a half due to mounting literacy [6]. Newspaper is local and hence a tangible mean of individual's empowerment [7].

While print dailies are struggling in much of the world, they are expected to boom in India as illustrated in Table I. It is apparent that newspapers have major share in Indian print industry and advertising is the key driver of the same. Moreover, print still maintains its stance as a powerful and necessary component of an advertisement campaign.

II. ADVERTISEMENT EFFECTIVENESS AND ITS ENABLERS

According to *Dictionary.com*, effectiveness is defined as the capability of producing a desired result. Another definition suggests that effectiveness is the degree to which objectives are achieved and the extent to which targeted problems are solved.

Advertisement effectiveness refers to how well a company's advertising accomplishes the intended [8]. It usually increases over time with many messages or exposures.

According to Corvi and Bonera, advertisement effectiveness is the extent to which advertising generates a certain desired effect [9]. An understanding of advertisement effectiveness would contribute significantly to the productivity of advertisers in terms of effective allocation of their marketing budgets [5]. Several researchers have investigated the research area of advertisement effectiveness with different viewpoints. A review of available literature suggests that research on advertisement effectiveness can be broadly categorized on the basis of different measures used in variety of advertising media as depicted in Fig. 2.

TABLE I
PRESENT AND PROJECTED SCENARIO OF INDIAN PRINT INDUSTRY

INR Billion	2012	2013	2014p	2015p	2016p	2017p	CAGR (2012-17)
Total Advertising	150	162	179	200	222	248	10.6%
Total Circulation	75	79	82	86	89	93	4.5%
Total Industry Size	224	241	261	285	311	340	8.7%
Total Newspaper Revenue	211	228	248	272	298	327	9.1%
Total Magazine Revenue	13	14	14	14	13	14	0.9%
Total Industry Size	224	241	261	285	311	340	8.7%

Source – KPMG in India Analysis, 2013 [10]

Few researchers have also studied the area of advertisement effectiveness through conceptual frameworks to understand the concept of advertisement effectiveness and how it can be measured.

Fig. 2 Classification of Advertising Literature

III. SELECT ENABLERS OF ADVERTISEMENT EFFECTIVENESS IN PRINT MEDIA

Based on the comprehensive and in-depth review of literature and discussion with subject experts and advertisement practitioners, numerous enablers have been recognized. However, most important select enablers are shown in Table II.

These enablers are identified keeping print media into context for Indian advertising scenario.

TABLE II
SELECT IMPORTANT ENABLERS OF ADVERTISEMENT EFFECTIVENESS

S.No.	Enabler	Reference
1.	Attention	[11]-[13]
2.	Interest	[14]-[16]
3.	Persuasion	[18], [19]
4.	Recall	[22], [23]
5.	Recognition	[25], [26]
6.	Purchase Intention	[27], [28]

These key enablers are described in detail in the following section.

A. Attention

It is one of the important enabler of advertisement effectiveness in context of print media. An effective advertisement is appealing [11], catchy [12], easily noticed and generates curiosity in the minds of target audience [13]. In

order to achieve advertisement efficacy, it is essential to be quick and direct to grab people's attention.

B. Interest

Though it is vital to attract the attention but generating interest and engaging target audience is equally essential and challenging. For an advertisement to be effective; it should be fascinating [14], alluring [15] and must be capable of holding potential customer's attention [16]. The most critical enablers to achieve interest are Attention [11]-[13] and Relevance [17]. Gaining the reader's interest is a deeper process than grabbing their attention.

C. Persuasion

As a major enabler of advertisement effectiveness in print media, persuasion encourages trial [18] and urges target audience to use the product or service in context [19]. Attention [11]-[13], Interest [15] and Liking [20] are most important enablers that lead to persuasion in print advertising perspective.

D. Recall

As a technique that explores memory for traces of awareness of an advertisement, recall approaches the memory indirectly [21]. Measuring recall is a fairly simple process and can be of aided or unaided nature. An effective advertisement is impressive [22], unforgettable [22] and easy to remember & recollect [23]. The most significant enablers to achieve recall are Persuasion [18] and Liking [20]. Several researchers have reported that the recall of rational commercials is higher than the recall of emotional ones [24].

E. Recognition

An effective advertisement is one which is easily noticeable [25], accepted by its target audience [26] and acknowledged without difficulty [25]. Recognition is a direct technique that attempts to access memory of an advertisement by prompting or trying to access any remembrance of having seen the advertisement before [24]. Similar to recall, Persuasion [19] and Liking [20] are critical enablers that lead to recognition in the context of print advertising.

F. Purchase Intention

As an enabler of advertisement effectiveness in print media, purchase intention facilitates to create customer desire [27], motivate customers to purchase [28] and incline target audience towards a product or service [27]. It is defined as an individual's readiness and willingness to purchase a certain

product or service [29].

According to Long and Ching [30], purchase intention stands for what we would like to buy in future. It is the decision to act that shows an individual's behavior according to the product [27]. It represents the possibility for consumers to buy a product or service [28]. The most critical enablers to attain purchase intention are Recall [23], Recognition [25], Persuasion [19] and Liking [20].

Fig. 3 Conceptual Framework of Advertisement Effectiveness

Considering the significance of identified enablers in context of print media, a conceptual framework of advertisement effectiveness is considered and represented in Fig. 3. It is clear that effectiveness of an advertisement in context of print media can be achieved only when these select enablers executed in an integrated way with due consideration to lead to association as identified through developed conceptual framework.

IV. CONCLUSION

It is evident that the area of measuring advertisement effectiveness has emerged as one of the important philosophies in recent times as huge sum of fund is involved in marketing and promotional activities. A clear understanding of advertisement effectiveness will contribute to allocation of advertising budgets optimally. An attempt has been made through this research study to identify select enablers of advertisement effectiveness in print context using an integrated approach. It also provides a comprehensive description of these enablers in context of print media.

A conceptual framework based on identified enablers is also presented which can be empirically tested using a systematic research method such as Interpretive Structural Modeling. The model provides useful insights and implications for practitioners and suggests paying more attention to recognized select enablers before developing an advertisement for print media in Indian context.

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